

BOUSSINESQ TIPIDAGI DIFFERENSIAL TENGLAMA UCHUN INTEGRAL SHART BILAN BERILGAN MASALA

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada $u_{tt}(t) + Au_{tt}(t) + Au(t) = f$ ko'rishidagi Boussinesq tipidagi tenglama uchun $u'(+0) = \psi$ va $\int_0^T u(t)dt = \varphi$ integral chegaraviy shartni qanoatlantiruvchi yechimni topish masalasi o'rganilgan, bu yerda $A: H \rightarrow H$ o'z-o'ziga qo'shma, chegaralanmagan, musbat H separabel Hilbert fazosida aniqlangan operator. Masalaning yechimining mavjud va yagonaligi Furye usulidan foydalanib ko'rsatilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Boussinesq tipidagi tenglama, integral chegaraviy shart, Hilbert fazosi, operator, Furye usuli.

Аннотация. В работе изучается задача нахождения решения, удовлетворяющего интегральным граничным условиям $u'(+0) = \psi$ и $\int_0^T u(t)dt = \varphi$ для уравнения типа Буссинеска вида $u_{tt}(t) + Au_{tt}(t) + Au(t) = f$, где $A: H \rightarrow H$ — самосопряженный, неограниченный, положительный H оператор, определенный в сепарабельном гильбертовом пространстве. Существование и единственность решения задачи доказаны с помощью метода Фурье.

Ключевая слова: Уравнение типа Буссинеска, интегральное граничное условие, гильбертово пространство, оператор, метод Фурье.

Annotation. The paper studies the problem of finding a solution satisfying the integral boundary conditions $u'(+0) = \psi$ and $\int_0^T u(t)dt = \varphi$ for the Boussinesq-type equation of the form $u_{tt}(t) + Au_{tt}(t) + Au(t) = f$, where $A: H \rightarrow H$ is a self-adjoint, unbounded, positive H separable operator defined in Hilbert space. The existence and uniqueness of the solution of the problem are shown using the Fourier method.

Keywords: Boussinesq - type equation, integral boundary condition, Hilbert space, operator, Fourier method.

Kirish

Ushbu maqolada Boussinesq tipidagi tenglama uchun integral chegaraviy shart bilan berilgan masala o'rganiladi.

Quyidagi masalani qaraylik:

$$\begin{cases} u_{tt}(t) + Au_{tt}(t) + Au(t) = f, & 0 < t \leq T, \\ \int_0^T u(t) dt = \varphi, \\ u'(0) = \phi, \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

bu yerda φ , ϕ va f – H Hilbert fazosining elementlari. $A: H \rightarrow H$ operator $D(A) \subset H$ aniqlanish sohasiga ega o‘z-o‘ziga qo‘shma, musbat, chegaralanmagan ixtiyoriy operator bo‘lsin. Faraz qilaylik, A operator H fazoda to‘la ortonormal $\{\mathcal{G}_k\}$ xos funksiyalar sistemasiga va mos ravishda $\{\lambda_k\}$ musbat xos sonlar to‘plamiga ega bo‘lsin. Shu bilan birga A operator xos sonlari ketma-ketligi noldan boshqa limit nuqtaga ega bo‘lmasin. Xos qiymatlarni qayta nomerlash yordamida ularni kamaymaydigan qilib nomerlab olamiz, ya’ni $0 < \lambda_1 \leq \lambda_2 \leq \dots \rightarrow +\infty$ kabi yozib olamiz.

Boussinesq xususiy hosilali differensial tenglamalari 1872 yilda Jozef Boussinesq tomonidan kiritilgan ([1] ga qarang) va u turli jarayonlarning modelini ifodalaydi. Boussinesq tenglamalari qatlamda suyuqlik sirtining harakatini (suyuqlik to‘lqin harakatlarini) tavsiflaydi, ya’ni suyuqlikning g‘ovakli idishdan oqib o‘tayotganda erkin sirtining shaklini ifodalaydi. Boussinesq tipidagi tenglamalar uchun boshlang‘ich va chegaraviy masalalar [2] - [10] maqolalarda o‘rganilgan. Ushbu [7] - [10] maqolalarda Boussinesq tipidagi tenglamalar uchun qo‘yilgan masalaning yechimi mavjud va yagonaligini ta’minlovchi shartlar olingan.

Ta’rif. Agar $u(t) \in C((0, T]; H)$ absolyut uzluksiz funksiya $u_{tt}(t), Au_{tt}(t), Au(t) \in C((0, T]; H)$ xossalarga ega bo‘lib, (1) masalaning barcha shartlarini qanoatlantirsa, u holda $u(t)$ funksiyaga (1) masalaning yechimi deyiladi.

Teorema. Agar $\varphi, \phi \in D(A)$, $f \in H$ va $\sin \mu_k T \neq 0$ bo‘lsin. U holda (1) masalaning yagona yechimi mavjud va u quyidagicha ko‘rinishga ega:

$$u(t) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\cos \mu_k t}{\sin \mu_k T} \left(\varphi_k \mu_k - \frac{f_k T \mu_k}{\lambda_k} + \frac{\phi_k \cos \mu_k T}{\mu_k} - \frac{\phi_k}{\mu_k} \right) \mathcal{G}_k + \left(\frac{f_k}{\lambda_k} + \frac{\phi_k}{\mu_k} \sin \mu_k t \right) \mathcal{G}_k,$$

bu yerda $\mu_k = \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_k}{1 + \lambda_k}}$.

In the inverse problem, a and b are found from the above result

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